

8T – Heavy Quark Decay

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Abstract:

By analyzing the new framework of varying curvature of manifolds, it is possible to present an analysis of heavy Quark decay. The analysis is built upon the idea of masses to be arbitrary amount of curvature converging inward, in contrast to the coupling constants series, which is arbitrary curvature diverging. Overtime there should be morphism between large amounts of curvature converging, and infinitesimal amounts of curvature, that is synonymous with heavy quark decay.

Introduction

The new 8T framework regards fermions as arbitrary variations of the Lorentz manifold, which was invoked stationary. We have proven fermions are formed by discretizing and partitioning the term δg into a series of sub elements in equation (1.1). Fermions and in particular quarks can be represented in equation (1.2):

$$s = (M, g)$$

$$\mathcal{L} = (s, s', t)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} - \left(\frac{d}{dt} \right) \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0, \quad -\frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\left[\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \right] \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \left[\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \right] \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

Since there is no data regarding the amount of curvature each of the two distinct element is possessing, it is an indication that there is a morphism between certain degrees of curvature overtime. That is supported by the Quark masses series, which describe an even number factorizations from the first family which is the (T-B) family to the (U-D) which is really the third family. That is given by one of two variations of an equation:

$$M_{N+1} = \frac{M_N + (7)}{7 * \prod_{E=1}^r N_E} * \frac{1}{9} \quad (2)$$

$$M_{N+1} = \frac{M_N + (7)}{7 * \prod_{E=1}^r N_E} \quad (2.1)$$

$$N_E = 2E ; E \geq 1$$

Meaning the next family in the series. Each family is composed as the total sum of the two M_{N+1} masses. The composition of mass is to indicate that each element is a subject of variance or a morphism to its complimentary element in the generation. That series gave us the prediction of a forth family below first generation, since the (+7) in equations (2) - (2.1) is in the numerator, nature will never be able to completely eliminate those converging curvatures and the result an in infinite series of families with decreasing mass, aspiring zero below fourth generation and overall stable over periods of time.

So overall, the only value needed to take into account is the sum of the two values of each generation. In the context of particle physics, we can conclude that given enough time as the manifold gets more and more flat, and the coupling series is developed over a longer and longer range toward weaker interactions, so does the family's masses gets infinitely smaller. We can represent a top Quark as a converging curvature of certain degree, that overtime is getting smaller and smaller, as nature would like to arbitrary variations to vanish, that is by devising in increasing amounts. Since there are only two elements, that the masses series allow morphisms among each generation.

The visualization above is meant to represent curvature converging getting infinitely smaller overtime due to the even numbers divisor functions (2) or (2.1). The ideas presented from that viewpoint are synonymous with heavy quark decay as one came to believe. Overall the distinction among distinct families and generations is quite not a real, in the 8T all we have is the manifold, some arbitrary amount of curvature are diverging, these are Bosonic matric tensor varying, isomorphic to primes or one as presented in equations (3) to (3.24), and some are converging, these are the masses.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (3)$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (3.1)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1):(24 + (3)) + 3:(120 + (3)) + 5:(840 + (3)) + 7 \dots \quad (3.21)$$

Switching to spin representation, using the prime critical line:

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} = 2N_1 + 1 \quad (3.21)$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} = 2N_2 + 1 \quad (3.22)$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} = 2N_3 + 1 \quad (3.23)$$

We have proven that the invariant three is the electron, and the discrete amount of net curvature is the photon as presented in (3.25), which is really a spinning curvature vortex:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (3.24)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta \gamma_i > 0 \quad (3.25)$$

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)
- [2] O. Manor. "The Quark Masses Series" In: (2021)
- [3] O. Manor. "The Coupling constants series, Spin Symmetries and Unbounded electrons" In: (2021)
- [4] O. Manor. "Proving Einstein Wrong – Gravity is a Short Range Interaction" In: (2021)